

JOANNA KOCOT-ZALEWSKA¹ , ANDRZEJ MELKE

The rove beetles (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae) from caves in the Częstochowa Upland

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¹ Upper Silesian Museum, Department of Natural History, pl. Jana III Sobieskiego 2, 41-902 Bytom,
Poland; email: j.kocot-zalewska@muzeum.bytom.pl, ORCID 0000-0002-9869-5837

Abstract: The paper refers rove beetles (Staphylinidae) from caves of the Częstochowa Upland (Poland). Currently, altogether 44 species are known from this area, three of them are eutroglophiles and nine subtroglophiles, others are considered as trogloxenes. The most common species is *Quedius mesomelinus mesomelinus*.

Key words: Staphylinidae, caves, Kraków-Częstochowa Upland, troglophiles, trogloxenes, ecology.

INTRODUCTION

The beetles are the most numerous order among all arthropods, with more than 400 thousand described species. The largest family are rove beetles (Staphylinidae) which represent various species that have an aptitude for inhabiting many types of environment, thus many of them have colonised undergrounds. These beetles represent ca 1 % of all known beetles from caves, which is less than ground beetles (Carabidae) or round fungus beetles (Leiodidae) (MOLDOVAN 2012), however, they are still important components of underground ecosystems. Plenty of cave-dwelling species of this family were described from Mediterranean region like Balkans (ABSOLON 1915), Morocco, Algeria, Italy, Spain (MOLDOVAN 2012), but also from caves in the temperate zone (ØSTBYE & LAURITZEN 2013, RŮŽIČKA *et al.* 2016, WEBER 2013, ZAENKER *et al.* 2020). In ecological classification they are usually troglophiles, just a few are troglobites (MOLDOVAN 2012).

Some information about rove beetles from Polish caves was published in various articles concerning general information about underground fauna, starting from the first work about cave fauna in Poland (DEMEL 1918). The most frequently mentioned species is *Quedius mesomelinus mesomelinus* (MARSHAM, 1802), which was listed by DEMEL 1918, PAX & MASCHKE 1935, KOWALSKI 1955, SKALSKI & WÓJCIK 1968, SKALSKI 1973 and 1981, GUBAŁA 1996, OCHMAN 2004. According to KOCOT-ZALEWSKA & DOMAGAŁA (2020), altogether 12 species from caves of Poland were known. Until today no article was devoted only to Staphylinidae inhabiting Polish caves. The purpose of this paper is a presentation a list of rove beetles inhabiting caves in the Częstochowa Upland with their ecological classification.

Fig. 1. Study area.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study on rove beetles was performed as a part of a larger project concerning invertebrates cave fauna in the Częstochowa Upland (KOCOT-ZALEWSKA *et al.* 2021, KOCOT-ZALEWSKA & WOŹNICA 2021). Study area (Fig. 1) and collecting methods were precisely described in KOCOT-ZALEWSKA & WOŹNICA (2021). The rove beetles were found in: W Zielonej Górze Cave, Towarna Cave, Pod Sokolą Cave, Kroczycka Cave, Psia Cave, and Zegarowa Cave.

All collected specimens were determined using various identification keys for Staphylinidae. Further, basing on available literature, habitat and food preferences were analysed (BURAKOWSKI *et al.* 1979, 1980, 1981, 2000, KOCH 1989a, 1989b, 1992, MAJKA *et al.* 2009, SMOLEŃSKI 2000, SZUJECKI 2008, 2017). Additionally, constant, seasonal or occasional inhabiting in caves was evaluated by frequency in different time of year, which was the first factor taken to the ecological classification.

The concept of ecological classification is based on SKET (2008), who divided organisms into four groups with different degree of association with undergrounds:

1. Troglobionts (= troglobites) – species very closely associated to caves, that live and reproduce in cave (SKET 2008), with many morphological, physiological and behavioural adaptations to undergrounds, like depigmentation, vestigial eyes, long chemosensors, elongated life cycle (WHITE & CULVER 2012).

2. Eutroglophiles – organisms generally live on surface, but also able to create stable populations in caves, with possibility to evolve into troglobites (SKET 2008).

3. Subtroglophiles – species which prefer temporary or continuously inhabiting caves but in their biology are associated with surface environment, for example feeding or reproducing outside the cave (SKET 2008).

4. Troglonexes – including all species that accidentally occupy caves, without capability to create stable underground population (SKET 2008).

RESULTS

Altogether 264 specimens belong to 44 species were collected from caves in the Cześćochowa Upland (Table 1). The most frequently collected species were: *Quedius mesomelinus mesomelinus* (MARSHAM, 1802), *Omalium caesum* GRAVENHORST, 1806, and *Atheta sodalis* (ERICHSON, 1837).

Habitat preferences have been ascertained for all collected species. Results are in Figure 2. Half of studied species prefer forests. Many species live under decaying matter, litter or in burrows and tree hollows.

Constant, seasonal or occasional inhabiting in caves was evaluated by frequency in different time of year. Below are presented species that occurred in caves during the whole year (or almost) in different parts of studied caves:

– entrance zone: *Anthobium atrocephalum* (GYLLENHAL, 1810), *Atheta sodalis*, *Omalium rivulare* (PAYKULL, 1789), *Othius punctulatus* (GOEZE, 1777), *O. subuliformis* STEPHENS, 1833, *Lesteva longoetytrata* (GOEZE, 1777), *Omalium excavatum* STEPHENS, 1834, *Syntomium aeneum* (MÜLLER, 1821);

– twilight zone: *Quedius mesomelinus mesomelinus*;

– deep zone: *Quedius mesomelinus mesomelinus*, *Omalium validum* KRAATZ, 1857, *Tachinus subterraneus* (LINNAEUS, 1758).

The other species were collected only once or in two seasons. The frequency for each species was analysed, the results are in the Table 1.

Just for 38% it was possible to ascertain food preferences. An equal number of species were carnivorous and detritivorous, and one was fungivorous (mycophagus).

Based on abovementioned information, the ecological classification was performed. Three species have been recognized as eutroglophiles, nine species as subtroglophiles, and other 32 species as troglonexes (Table 1).

Table 1. The list of species with marked seasonality, cave' number in which species was detected, and ecological classification. **1** – W Zielonej Górze, **2** – Towarna, **3** – Pod Sokolą, **4** – Kroczycka, **5** – Psia, **6** – Zegarowa.

N°	Species	Seasonality				Cave number	Ecological classification
		Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter		
1.	<i>Acidota cruentata</i> MANNERHEIM, 1830					2,3	trogloxene
2.	<i>Anotylus inustus</i> (Gravenhorst, 1806)					6	trogloxene
3.	<i>Anotylus sculpturatus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)					6	trogloxene
4.	<i>Anthobium atrocephalum</i> (GYLLENHAL, 1810)					1,3,4,6	subtroglophile
5.	<i>Atheta crassicornis</i> (FABRICIUS, 1793)					1,6	trogloxene
6.	<i>Atheta fungi</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)					1	trogloxene

N°	Species	Seasonality				Cave number	Ecological classification
		Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter		
7.	<i>Atheta gyllenhalii</i> (THOMSON, 1856)					3	trogloxene
8.	<i>Atheta ravilla</i> (ERICHSON, 1839)					1,3	trogloxene
9.	<i>Atheta sodalis</i> (ERICHSON, 1837)					1,3,4,5,6	subtroglophile
10.	<i>Autalia longicornis</i> SCHEERPELTZ, 1947					1,3	trogloxene
11.	<i>Bryaxis puncticollis</i> (DENNY, 1825)					5	trogloxene
12.	<i>Bryophacis crassicornis</i> ((MÄKLIN, 1847)					3	trogloxene
13.	<i>Bythinus macropalpus</i> AUBÉ, 1833					6	trogloxene
14.	<i>Dinaraea angustula</i> (GYLLENHAL, 1810)					3	trogloxene
15.	<i>Dinothenarus fossor</i> (SCOPOLI, 1771)					3	trogloxene
16.	<i>Domene scabricollis</i> (ERICHSON, 1840)					6	trogloxene
17.	<i>Gabrius breviventer</i> (SPERK, 1835)					3	trogloxene
18.	<i>Ischnosoma longicorne</i> (MÄKLIN, 1847)					4	trogloxene
19.	<i>Lesteva longoelytrata</i> (GOEZE, 1777)					3,6	subtroglophile
20.	<i>Liogluta alpestris</i> (HEER, 1839)					1,4	trogloxene
21.	<i>Mycetoporus clavicornis</i> (STEPHENS, 1832)					1	trogloxene
22.	<i>Ocalea picata</i> (STEPHENS, 1832)					3	trogloxene
23.	<i>Ocypus macrocephalus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)					6	trogloxene
24.	<i>Omalium caesum</i> GRAVENHORST, 1806					1,3,5,6	subtroglophile
25.	<i>Omalium excavatum</i> STEPHENS, 1834					1,6	subtroglophile
26.	<i>Omalium rivulare</i> (PAYKULL, 1789)					1,6	subtroglophile
27.	<i>Omalium validum</i> KRAATZ, 1857					5,6	eutroglophile
28.	<i>Othius punctulatus</i> (GOEZE, 1777)					3,4,5	subtroglophile
29.	<i>Othius subuliformis</i> STEPHENS, 1833					1,4	subtroglophile
30.	<i>Oxypoda acuminata</i> (STEPHENS, 1832)					4	trogloxene
31.	<i>Oxypoda annularis</i> (MANNERHEIM, 1830)					1,3	trogloxene

N°	Species	Seasonality				Cave number	Ecological classification
		Spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter		
32.	<i>Oxyptoda praecox</i> ERICHSON, 1839					2	trogloxene
33.	<i>Philonthus decorus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)					3	trogloxene
34.	<i>Phloeonomus punctipennis</i> THOMSON, 1867					3	trogloxene
35.	<i>Proteinus brachypterus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1792)					3,4	trogloxene
36.	<i>Quedius limbatus</i> (HEER, 1839)					3	trogloxene
37.	<i>Quedius mesomelinus mesomelinus</i> (MARSHAM, 1802)					1,2,3,4,5,6	eutroglophile
38.	<i>Sepedophilus marshami</i> (STEPHENS, 1832)					2	trogloxene
39.	<i>Staphylinus erythropterus</i> LINNAEUS, 1758					1	trogloxene
40.	<i>Syntomium aeneum</i> (MÜLLER, 1821)					6	subtroglophile
41.	<i>Tachinus subterraneus</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)					1,6	eutroglophile
42.	<i>Xantholinus laevigatus</i> JACOBSEN, 1849					4	trogloxene
43.	<i>Xantholinus linearis</i> (OLIVIER, 1795)					2	trogloxene
44.	<i>Xantholinus longiventris</i> HEER, 1839					1	trogloxene

Fig. 2. Habitat preferences of the examined rove beetles.

DISCUSSION

Results obtained in this study increase our knowledge about rove beetles inhabiting caves in Poland. Only 12 species were known from this environment so far (KOCOT-ZALEWSKA & DOMAGAŁA 2020), while nowadays it is 44. It's a significant result in view of the fact that previous data concerned a few cave regions in Poland like whole Kraków-Częstochowa Upland, Sudety Mts., Tatra Mts. and Świętokrzyski Region, whereas our results concern only one, quite small region.

The most frequently collected species was *Quedius mesomelinus mesomelinus*. It is a typical eutroglophile occurring in many caves in Europe, and widely in the Palearctic region (SALNITSKA & SOLODOVNIKOV 2019). This species was introduced to Greenland, the Australian region, North and South America (LÖBL & LÖBL 2015, SALNITSKA & SOLODOVNIKOV 2019). It was known also from previous study in Polish caves (DEMEL 1918, PAX & MASCHKE 1935, KOWALSKI 1955, SKALSKI & WÓJCIK 1968, SKALSKI 1973, GUBAŁA 1996). As an eutroglophile are also considered *Tachinus subterraneus* and *Omalium validum*, because specimens of both species occurred in the studied caves during the whole year and inhabited the deep part of them, which proves existing undergrounds populations. Both species prefer living in burrows (BURAKOWSKI *et al.* 1979, 1980). Additionally, *T. subterraneus* and *O. validum* have been previously known from caves. The first one from Tatra Mts. (KOWALSKI 1955), Czech Republic (MLEJNEK *et al.* 2015) and Germany (ZAENKER *et al.* 2020), and the second one from Luxemburg (in the collection of the Luxemburg National Museum of Natural History), Czech Republic (MLEJNEK *et al.* 2015) and Germany (ZAENKER *et al.* 2020).

As many as nine species were considered as subtroglaphiles (Table 1). Every species in this class has been caught in the entrance zone of studied caves. It was found also in a pitfall in front of caves. Some species, like *Atheta sodalis*, *Lesteva longoelytrata*, *Omalium caesum*, *O. rivulare*, *Syntomium aeneum* are known from Luxemburgish caves. Others, like *Anthobium atrocephalum*, *O. rivulare*, *Othius punctulatus* are known from the Mesovoid Shallow Substratum environment in Slovakia (RENDOŠ *et al.* 2012). The organisms, that live in MSS (JUBERTHIE *et al.* 1980, WHITE & CULVER 2012), prefer lack of light and high value of air humidity but tolerate considerable amplitude of air temperature. These organisms have often similar morphological adaptations as cave obligatory dwellers (PIPAN & CULVER 2012). All subtroglaphiles are also known from caves and MSS in Czech Republic (MLEJNEK *et al.* 2015). The analyses of accessible information about food and habitat preferences (BURAKOWSKI *et al.* 1979, 1980, 1981, 2000, Koch 1989a, 1989b, 1992, MAJKA *et al.* 2009, SMOLEŃSKI 2000, SZUJECKI 2008, 2017) shows that these species prefer shadow areas – under stones, in a litter and fallen leaves, and they feed decaying matter or are predators. Thus, we can assume, that these species do not penetrate caves accidentally, but actively.

SUMMARY

The list of the Staphylinidae species known from Polish caves increased more than twice. Previously only 12 species were known, while currently 44 species are recognized. Nowadays three eutroglophiles and nine subtroglaphiles are identified in caves of Poland. The most common species is *Quedius mesomelinus mesomelinus*.

REFERENCES

- ABSOLON K. 1915. Bericht über höhlenbewohnende Staphyliniden der dinarischen und angrenzenden Karstgebiete. *Coleopterologische Rundschau* 11(12): 132–151.
- BURAKOWSKI B., MROCZKOWSKI M., STEFAŃSKA J. 1979. Chrząszcze – Coleoptera. Kusakowate – Staphylinidae, Cz. 1. *Katalog fauny Polski* 23(6): 1–310.
- BURAKOWSKI B., MROCZKOWSKI M., STEFAŃSKA J. 1980. Chrząszcze – Coleoptera. Kusakowate – Staphylinidae, Cz. 2. *Katalog fauny Polski* 23(7): 1–271.
- BURAKOWSKI B., MROCZKOWSKI M., STEFAŃSKA J. 1981. Chrząszcze – Coleoptera. Kusakowate – Staphylinidae, Cz. 3: Aleocharinae. *Katalog fauny Polski* 23(8): 1–329.
- BURAKOWSKI B., MROCZKOWSKI M., STEFAŃSKA J. 2000. Chrząszcze – Coleoptera. Uzupełnienia tomów 2-21. *Katalog fauny Polski* 23(22): 1–252.
- DEMEL K. 1918. Fauna jaskiń Ojcowskich. *Sprawozdania z posiedzeń Towarzystwa Naukowego Warszawskiego, Wydział Nauk Matematyczno-Przyrodniczych* 11(4): 623–659.
- GUBALA J. 1996. Fauna jaskiń regionu świętokrzyskiego- podsumowanie wyników badań z lat 1994-1996, pp. 19–20, In: *Materiały XXX Sympozjum Speleologicznego, Kielce-Bocheniec*.
- JUBERTHE C., DELAY B., BOUILLON M. 1980. Extension du milieu souterrain en zone non-calcaire: description d'un nouveau milieu et de son peuplement par les Coléoptères troglobies. *Mémoires Biospéologie* 7: 19–52.
- KOCH K. 1989a. Die Käfer Mitteleuropas. Ökologie. Goecke & Evers, Krefeld: 440 pp.
- KOCH K. 1989b. Die Käfer Mitteleuropas. Ökologie. Band 2. Goecke & Evers, Krefeld: 382 pp.
- KOCH K. 1992. Die Käfer Mitteleuropas. Ökologie. Band 3. Goecke & Evers, Krefeld: 389 pp.
- KOCOT-ZALEWSKA J., DOMAGAŁA P. 2020. Terrestrial invertebrate fauna of Polish caves – a summary of 100 years of research. *Subterranean Biology* 33: 45–69. <https://doi.org/10.3897/subtbiol.33.48805>.
- KOCOT-ZALEWSKA J., DOMAGAŁA P.J., LIS B. 2021. Living in isolation for almost 40 years: molecular divergence of the 28S rDNA and COI sequences between French and Polish populations of the cave beetle *Speonomus normandi hydrophilus* (JEANNEL, 1907). *Subterranean Biology* 37: 75–88. <https://doi.org/10.3897/subtbiol.37.54720>.
- KOCOT-ZALEWSKA J., WOŹNICA A.J. 2021. Cave-dwelling heleomyzid flies (Diptera: Heleomyzidae) from the Polish caves. Historical overview and new data. *International Journal of Speleology* 50(2): 203–211. <https://doi.org/10.5038/1827-806X.50.2.2383>.
- KOWALSKI K. 1955. Fauna jaskiń Tatr Polskich. *Ochrona Przyrody* 23: 283–333.
- LÖBL I., LÖBL D. 2015. Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Hydrophiloidea Staphylinoidea. Part 2. Revised and updated edition. Brill, Boston: 1702 pp.
- MAJKA C.G., MICHAUD J-P., MOREAU G. 2009. Adventive species of *Quedius* (Coleoptera, Staphylinidae) in North America: a survey and new Canadian record. 209, pp. 341–345, In: MAJKA C.G., KLIMASZEWSKI J. (Eds), Biodiversity, Biosystematics, and Ecology of Canadian Coleoptera II. *ZooKeys* 22.
- MĚJNEK R., HAMET A., RŮŽIČKA J. 2015. Beetles (Coleoptera) in caves and chasms of the Czech Republic. *Acta Speleologica* 6: 1–112.
- MOLDOVAN E. 2012. Beetles, pp. 96-107, In: WHITE W.B., CULVER D.C (Eds), Encyclopedia of caves. Academic Press.
- OCHMAN K. 2004. Fauna jaskiń rezerwatu „Sokole Góry” – koncepcja jej ochrony w świetle dotychczasowych badań. Zróżnicowanie i przemiany środowiska przyrodniczo-kulturowego Wyżyny Krakowsko-Częstochowskiej. T. 1, *Przyroda*: 89–95.
- ØSTBYE E., LAURITZEN S-E. 2013. A checklist of invertebrates from Norwegian caves and mines. *Fauna norvegica* 33: 35–51.
- PAX F., MASCHKE K. 1935. Höhlenfauna des Glatzer Schneeberges. Die rezente Metazoenfauna. *Beiträge zur Biologie des Glatzer Schneeberges* 1: 4–72.
- RENDŐS M., MOCK A., JÁSZAY T. 2012. Spatial and temporal dynamics of invertebrates dwelling karstic mesovoid shallow substratum of Sivec National Nature Reserve (Slovakia), with emphasis on Coleoptera. *Biologia* 67/6: 1143–1151.
- RŮŽIČKA V., MĚJNEK R., JUŘIČKOVÁ L., TAJOVSKÝ K., ŠMILAUER P., ZAJÍČEK P. 2016. Invertebrates of The Macocha Abyss (Moravian Karst, Czech Republic). *Acta Carsologica* 45/1: 71–84.
- SALNITSKA M., SOLODOVNIKOV A. 2019. Rove beetles of the genus *Quedius* (Coleoptera, Staphylinidae) of Russia: a key to species and annotated catalogue. *ZooKeys* 847: 1–100. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.847.34049>.
- SKALSKI A., WÓCİK Z. 1968. Jaskinie rezerwatu Sokole Góry w okolicy Częstochowy. Ochrona Przyrody PAN, Kraków: 237–275.
- SKALSKI A.W. 1973. Materiały do znajomości bezkręgowców jaskiń Wyżyny Krakowsko-Częstochowskiej. *Rocznik Muzeum Częstochowskiego* (3): 161–200.
- SKALSKI A.W. 1981. Charakterystyka fauny podziemnej Wyżyny Krakowsko-Częstochowskiej. *Rocznik Muzeum Okręgowego w Częstochowie* 5, *Przyroda* 2: 51–60.
- SKET B. 2008. Can we agree on an ecological classification of subterranean animals? *Journal of Natural History* 42(21): 1549–1563. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222930801995762>.

- SMOLEŃSKI M. 2000. Kusakowate (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae) borów bazyńowych (*Empetro-nigri Pinetum*) Mierzei Łebskiej w Słowińskim Parku Narodowym. *Wiadomości entomologiczne* 18(4): 207–222.
- SZUJECKI A. 2008. *Klucze do oznaczania owadów Polski*. Cz. XIX. Chrząszcze – Coleoptera. Zeszyt 24a. Kusakowate – Staphylinidae. Polskie Towarzystwo Entomologiczne. Toruń: 215 pp.
- SZUJECKI A. 2017. Kusakowate (Staphylinidae) lasów Polski. Aspekt różnorodności i monitoringu zooindykacyjnego. Lasy Państwowe, Warszawa: 150 pp.
- WEBER D. 2013. Die Höhlenfauna Luxemburgs. *Ferrantia* 69, Musée national d'histoire naturelle, Luxembourg: 408 pp.
- WHITE W.B., CULVER D.C. 2012. *Encyclopedia of caves*. Academic Press: 945 pp.
- ZÄENKER S., WEBER D., WEIGAND A. 2020. Liste der cavernicolen Tierarten Deutschlands mit Einschluss der Grundwasserfauna (Version 1.9). [accessed 27.04.2020]. Available from URL: <https://www.hoehlentier.de/taxa.pdf>.

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